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ABSTRACT

We present the design of a variable temperature setup that uses a pulse tube cryocooler to perform break-junction experiments at variable temperatures ranging from 12 K to room temperature. The use of pulse tube coolers is advantageous because they are easy to use, can be highly automatized, and used to avoid wastage of cryogenic fluids. This is the reason why dry cryostats are conquering more and more fields in cryogenic physics. However, the main drawback is the level of vibration that can be up to several micrometers at the cold-head. The vibrations make the operation of scanning probe-based microscopes challenging. We implemented vibration-damping techniques that allow obtaining a vibration level of 12 pm between the tip and sample. With these adaptations, we show the possibility to perform break junction measurements in a cryogenic environment and keep in place atomic chains of a few nanometers between the two electrodes.

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INTRODUCTION

Transport measurements of heat and charge at atomic and molecular scales have benefited tremendously from scanning probe microscopy and related techniques. For example, to probe quantum transport properties, break junction (BJ) experiments based on scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) have become a major working horse to characterize atomic and molecular junctions. In STM-BJs, two electrodes, the metal tip and the metal surface, are brought in contact and then slowly separated. In this way, it is possible to slowly thin down their contact to the atomic level and pull out from the substrate a single atom or even linear chains of atoms, which can then be studied in terms of their physical properties. In break junctions, quantization effects are routinely used as models to study electrical, thermal, and mechanical properties down to the atomic scale at different temperatures.^{1–5} Because of a clear quantum nature and their atomic size, those junctions are often referred to as “quantum point contacts” (QPCs).

Transport physics involves various effects, ranging from hopping to tunneling, quantum interference, and magnetic correlations.

To clearly separate and characterize these effects, it is often necessary to vary the temperature of the experiment over a wide range, from above room temperature to cryogenic temperatures. Bath cryostat setups allowing variable temperature operation consume considerable amounts of liquid helium, which is both costly and demanding for the operator. Pulse tube coolers (PTCs), in contrast, recycle helium in a closed-cycle operation. PTCs require less handling, are most cost-efficient, and can be remotely controlled, compared to standard wet refrigerators. However, even though they can be built without moving parts at low temperatures, the main drawback with pulse tubes is indeed the level of vibration, which, in most cases, is about several micrometers at the cold end. The formation and study of QPCs by STM-break junction techniques require a significant level of mechanical stability (below 1 Å) that is in contrast with the vibration levels of PTCs, for which micrometer level amplitudes are considered already ambitious,^{6,7} a prohibitive level in the case of sensitive techniques, such as scanning probes.

The reason is that pulse tubes rely on a periodic compression of the working gas, usually helium, inside the refrigerator. The periodic change in pressure causes a periodic elastic deformation

that connects the cryocooler flange to the aluminum crossbar and allows changing the height of the cryocooler with respect to the vacuum chamber where it will be inserted for the experiment. The vacuum chamber, instead, is placed on a table (4) standing on the isolated concrete slab (5a). The only mechanical link connecting the cryocooler flange to the vacuum chamber is a flexible stainless-steel bellows (6), which provides the first stage of damping. Right below the bellows, there is a flange for the electrical feedthrough (7) and then a supporting flange to which an aluminum shield (9) is mechanically hung by means of four low thermal conductivity glass-fiber rods (8) (diameter $\varnothing = 6$ mm, thermal conductivity $k_{th} \approx 0.7$ W m⁻¹ K⁻¹). The aluminum shields are gold plated using electroplating to increase the emissivity. The shield is thermally connected to the first stage of the cryocooler at 50 K through flexible copper braids (OFHC grade, $k_{th} \approx 395$ W m⁻¹ K⁻¹, thickness = 2 mm). Like this, the shield is thermally strongly connected and mechanically weakly connected to the first stage. At the same time, the shield is mechanically strongly connected and thermally weakly connected to the supporting flange.

Inside the shield, a first copper platform is attached to the inner part of the shield through another set of the same glass-fiber rods. The copper platform is then thermally linked to the second stage of the pulse tube cooler at 4 K by means of a second series of copper braids like the ones above. This stage is used to thermalize all the wires [24× silver-plated copper twisted pair (34-AWG) plus 4× copper single wires (24-AWG)] by clamping them to six copper bobbins attached to the stage itself. Then, a second copper platform (11), situated below the first one, holds the microscope head and it is mechanically suspended to the upper platform via a combination of stiff rods and custom made Be-Cu springs (10) (spring constant ~ 150 N/m at room temperature). In order to provide an optimal thermal link, a braided copper strip (thickness = 0.5 mm), shaped like a spiral to reduce stiffness, goes around each spring, connecting the two stiff rods (10). At the scanning stage (11), a sample carrier (FerroVac SHOME13) is placed on a stack of piezoelectric elements consisting of two positioners (Attocube ANPx101) for the coarse motion in the XY-plane and one open loop xyz-scanner

(Attocube ANSxyz100) to guarantee sub-nanometer resolution during STM-break junction measurements. The thermalization of the sample carrier is guaranteed by the attachment of an additional flexible copper wire to the scanning stage. Finally, to allow for a variable operating temperature of the microscope, a heater [50 Ω resistor (12)] is attached to the bottom of the scanning copper stage and regulated via a temperature controller (Lakeshore 335). The total mass (mainly the copper base plate) of the load connected to the second stage is ~ 1.7 kg.

Cooling operation

The system is able to reach a temperature of 12 K, overall limited by the thermal conduction of the cabling involved and the thermal coupling of the shield to the first cooling stage. However, in the selection of the cooler, the low level of vibration has been preferred over cooling capabilities. In the case under consideration, the anticipated experiments are also rather slow. Therefore, a large copper mass could be used to avoid thermal fluctuations, leading, in return, to relatively long cool down times. Usually, a minimum temperature of 12 K is steadily reached after 9 h of cooling from room temperature. The STM operation does not induce any significant additional heat load and no temperature rise is observed during the operation (Fig. 2).

CHARACTERIZATION METHODS

Vibration

Within the system, there is interest to measure the vibration levels at two locations, at the second stage of the PTC and at the STM head, to probe the relative motion of the tip with respect to a sample surface. The vibration levels at the PTC are measured using accelerometers (Bruel and Kjaer, Type 4506-B-003, BW = 0.3–1200 Hz) mounted directly on the second stage. Measurements were recorded at room temperature directly after starting the PTC operation because sensors mounting are not suited for UHV and low temperature operation. The measured power spec-

FIG. 2. Picture of the setup with the thermal radiation shield. In the box, a close-up view of the scanning stage suspended via Be-Cu springs.

FIG. 3. Vibration specifications of the pulse tube cooler measured at the second stage: (a) rms spectrum (the black arrow indicates the main frequency of vibration at 1.2 Hz). The resolution bandwidth is 0.1 Hz. (b) Amplitude of displacement at 1.2 Hz.

trum of vibration was then numerically integrated twice to calculate the displacement spectrum over a 20 Hz bandwidth [see Fig. 3(a)].

To measure the vibration amplitudes in the microscope head, we make use of the strong distance dependence of a tunneling current between the STM tip and surface. To this end, we use a gold STM tip and a 150 nm-thick gold layer deposited on a silicon chip. The tip is chemically etched¹⁵ from a 250 μm pure gold wire (Goodfellow AU005140), then rinsed in de-ionized (DI) water and isopropanol, and finally dried under nitrogen flow. The gold surface of the chip is cleaned by flame annealing, wire-bonded to a chip carrier, and then loaded into the vacuum chamber.

The net displacement between the tip and the sample is calculated inverting the equation $I(z) \propto I_0 e^{-2kz}$, where z is the distance between the two electrodes, I is the tunneling current, I_0 is a suitable parameter, while k is the inverse decay length specific to the material. As k is sensitive to the exact work function of the sample and

tip, we measure $m = 2k$ each time before and after performing a new measurement of vibration. The measured values of m range from 0.1 to 0.8 \AA^{-1} . A schematic of the measurement technique is depicted in Fig. 4(a). The amplifier used is a low noise current-to-voltage converter (SP983c from Basel Precision Instruments) with a gain of 10^7 V/A. The acquisition time interval is set to 10 s with a sampling time of 1 ms so that the accessible frequency range spans from 0.1 to 500 Hz. In this way, all frequencies relevant to STM-BJ operation, including the low frequencies typical of pulse tube oscillation of 1–2 Hz, can be probed.

Break junction measurements

Break junction traces are acquired right after vibration measurements by approaching the tip of the microscope into contact with the counter electrode (closing trace) and slowly retracting it apart (opening trace). The closing trace stops when a conductance

FIG. 4. (a) Schematic for the measurement of the net tip–surface displacement. (b) Raw displacement trace, including low frequency drift, from STM current recorded over an acquisition period of 10 s and its relative rms value (σ).

of $G_{el} = \frac{I_{stm}}{V_{bias}} = 10G_0$ is reached. Here, $G_0 = \frac{2e^2}{h} = 7.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$ S is the quantum of electrical conductance. The speed for both approach and retraction from the surface is set to 7 nm/s.

CHARACTERIZATION OF VIBRATIONAL NOISE AND ITS EFFECTS

Vibration of the cryocooler

For comparison, Fig. 3 displays the measurement of the vibration level of the second stage of the PTC during operation of the PTC and in the idle stage. Figure 3(a) shows the rms-displacement spectrum for the z -axis over a 20 Hz bandwidth. A peak around ~ 1.2 Hz, a signature of the pulse tube cooler, is clearly visible, together with higher frequency harmonics. In Fig. 3(b), the mechanical oscillations recorded by the accelerometer are plotted over a 3-s period. For this plot, the low-frequency drift visible in Fig. 3(a) was removed using a high-pass filter to visualize better the vibration level induced by the operation of the PTC. The peak amplitude of the signal vs time is equal to $\pm 72.6 \mu\text{m}$ and the rms-amplitude to $35.6 \mu\text{m}$.

Net displacement

Next, we turn to measurements of the vibration inside the microscope head. A schematic of the measurement technique is depicted in Fig. 4(a). For the measurements, we chose a temperature of 45 K after a week of cooling operation, which represents a typical experimental scenario. A vibration trace of 10 s, with the rms-value as low as 11.8 pm, could be recorded and is presented in Fig. 4(b). We note that vibration levels vary throughout the day but were never worse than 65 pm (see the [supplementary material](#)). Those levels are manageable for scanning probe measurements and compare well to other systems using PTC cryocoolers for sensitive measurements. Our system has vibration levels lower than other dry-cryostat setups using single-stage damping techniques, which feature rms-values of 65 pm or higher,^{8,9} and it is in the same range of vibrations of other setups utilizing more sophisticated multi-stage

methods, showing a cumulated displacement of 60 pm over almost a 10 kHz bandwidth.¹⁰

We suppose that the reason for such high stability and small net displacement between the tip and sample can be attributed, in part, to the stillness of the lab and to the mechanical decoupling of the cold head from the rest of the setup but mainly to the series combination of springs, empirically selected to have the right elasticity to act as a “low-pass” filter for vibrations and the “high-pass” filter due to the rigid connection of the tip holder and sample carrier to the scanning stage. We note, however, that the comparison between the vibration of the pulse tube’s second stage and the tip–sample gap does not mean that the pulse-tube itself has been reduced in vibration. Instead, we isolated the tip–sample system from the noise created at the second stage of the pulse tube.

BREAK-JUNCTION OPERATION

To demonstrate the capability of the instrument to operate during break-junction experiments, we performed a break junction measurement at 45 K. During the experiment, the tip is repeatedly brought into (closing trace) and out of contact (opening trace) with the sample. The electrical conductance measured during such break-junction events demonstrates the hallmark of quantization steps and the thinning down of the junction down to single-atom diameters. An important criterion for the usability of good transport measurements is the temporal stability of the junction. Ideally, a junction plateau (the conductance being on a defined and narrow range of values) is long enough in time (or pulling distance) to enable detailed measurements.^{2,16}

Because of the great stability of the system, the quantization of the electrical conductance is observable up to $8 G_0$ (see Fig. 5). Indeed, each quantization step represents the number of atoms (or monoatomic filaments) bridging the two electrodes, each one carrying a single quantum of electrical conductance G_0 . To check for spurious events, we performed 2300 measurements and combined them in a 1D histogram [see Fig. 6(a)]. More than 90% of the traces

FIG. 5. Opening trace of a break junction measurement at 45 K.

FIG. 6. One-dimensional histograms showing (a) peaks at multiples of the electrical conductance quantum G_0 and (b) length of the plateaus at 1 G_0 .

(2127 out of 2300) show a plateau of at least five datapoints in the range (0.9–1.1) G_0 . For those selected traces, we calculate the length of the plateau at G_0 , showing how the stability of the system allows the formation of long single-atom filaments up to several Angstroms in length with a good percentage of traces (~25%) going above 1 nm [Fig. 6(b)]. We note that this distance suggests pulling atomic chains. To estimate the number of atoms in such chains, the reported values for the radius of a gold atom, varying from 1.35 to 1.96 Å,^{17–19} can be considered, together with a stretched Au–Au bond distance around 3.6 Å.²⁰ Figure 6(b) does not show obvious peaks at exact multiples of the aforesaid values but ultimately illustrates the possibility to uphold nanometric single-atom wires.

OUTLOOK AND CONCLUSION

We have designed a system to maintain a vibration level constantly below 65 pm between a STM tip and a sample, and that under optimal conditions of the lab, this level reduces further down to 11.8 pm. This allows for the measurement of break junctions at variable temperatures with a pulse tube cryostat.

Compared to previously reported systems, the present setup reaches competitive vibration levels with a single-stage damping system and without the need for more elaborated damping solutions, such as cascaded mass-spring systems. Further improvement appears possible using, for example, an eddy-current damper installed between the bottom of the experimental stage and the shield to further reduce vibrations. Possible improvements for reaching lower temperature consist of using more resistive wires for lines that do not carry the signal (piezos and temperature sensors) and/or reducing the diameter of the same. However, with the current modifications, we already reached a level of vibrations that allows us to run a break junction experiment with sub-Å mechanical noise at variable temperatures and extract, from a gold surface, single-atom filaments stretching over more than 1 nm before rupture.

We hope that the description of our STM break-junction experiment in a pulse tube-driven cryostat can also help design other

cryogenic setups, especially with the present trend toward dry systems in cryogenics.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The [supplementary material](#) contains further datasets [like Fig. 4(b)] on vibration measurements during different times of the day.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

A.G. and B.G. designed the setup with input from A.K.; A.G., A.Z., F.H., and B.G. built the setup; A.G. performed the measurements and analyzed them with input from B.G., M.C., and S.F.; A.G. and B.G. wrote the manuscript with input from all authors.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The raw data of the measurements discussed here are found in the [supplementary material](#).

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